

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE NORTHERN AND SOUTHERN NETWORK OF THE GREAT SILK ROAD IN AMIR TEMUR'S RELATIONS WITH CHINA

Kenjaev Sardor

Pedagogical Institute of Bukhara State University,
teacher of the Department of Social

+998931445555 sardorkenjaye46@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7456181>

Abstract: The importance of the Northern and Southern network of the Great Silk Road in Amir Temur's relations with China. Amir Temur's relations with China were also discussed in terms of trade, social, economic and military spheres.

Key words: Great Silk Road, China and Central Asia, Khorezm trade caravan, trade-economic, northern network. It is noteworthy that in the Middle Ages the Great Silk Road was more active and crowded than in ancient times. This was due to the patronage of the trade development of large empires established in China, Central Asia and the Middle East, such as the Tang Empire (618-907 AD), the Arab Caliphate (632-1258 AD), and the Samani State (865-999 AD). The trade of the Silk Road, which has been active for many centuries, decreased for a while as a result of the Mongol invasion, which had a negative impact on the development of China and Central Asian countries by the 13th century, and it can be seen that only its northern branch developed. Academician V.V. Barthold acknowledges the Khorezm trade caravan that went to Kashgar in 1209-1210, mentioned in Saadi Shirazi's work "Gulistan", as the last major international trade caravan of the 13th century (except, of course, for the short-term economic and diplomatic relations between Khorezmshah and Genghis Khan). In our opinion, V.V. Barthold's opinion is not so correct. Because Plano Carpini, Guillaume de Rubruck, Marco Polo, Ricoldo de Monte Croce, John de Montecorvino, Thomas Mangazola, Francis and Raymond Rufus and many other European Christian ambassadors, merchants, and missionaries entered Central Asia and China through trade caravans. From the information left by some of them, it is not difficult to understand that trade and economic relations did not stop at all.

By the 14th century, the trade between China and the Central Asian countries started to develop again under new conditions. Of course, the rulers of the Golden Horde (1236-1481) and the Khuloku dynasty in Iran (1256-1358, also known as the Elkhanid state) were interested in this. Gradually, the northern branch of the ancient Silk Road rose as the main route. In the 14th

century, along this northern road, trade caravans from the capital of the Golden Horde - Saray to Ustyurt, Urganch, O'tror, Tashkent, Almalyk - were constantly traveling to China. At this time, trade was carried out on this route with the countries of the Middle East through the Caucasus, and in the north with the Russian principalities and the countries of Eastern Europe.

Amir Temur was certainly not indifferent to the events taking place in the neighboring countries. Because these events had a direct impact on the socio-economic life in Movarounnahr. He initially supported the installation of Tokhtamysh (1380-1395), a descendant of Jo'chi, on the throne of the Golden Horde, but later these two rulers became conflicting neighbors. During his campaign against Tokhtamysh Khan in 1395, Amir Temur captured the lower Volgaboyi and its central cities, Saray Berka, Saray Botu and Hojitarkhan (Astrakhan). The attack on these cultural centers of the Golden Horde by the troops of Amir Temur undermined trade in the northern network. As a result, the large cities of the Golden Horde could not recover economically for a long time. In this way, the network of northern trade routes that connected China with the countries of the Middle East ended. Now, all the trade traffic began to pass through the large commercial and cultural cities of the Timurid Empire (1370-1507).

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Амир Темур жаҳон тарихида / Масъул муҳаррир: Ҳ.Кароматов. Муаллифлар жамоаси: С.Саидқосимов (раҳбар), А.Аҳмедов, Б.Аҳмедов ва бошқ. Тўлдирилган ва қайта ишланган иккинчи нашри. – Т.: Шарқ, 2001. – Б.121.
2. Ҳавофий Фасиҳ Аҳмад. “Мужмали Фасиҳий”дан // Амир Темур ва Улуғбек замондошлари хотирасида: (Рисола) / Б.Аҳмедов, У.Уватов, Ғ.Каримов ва бошқ. – Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1996. – Б.218.
3. Йаздий Шарафуддин Али. Зафарнома // Сўзбоши, табдил, изоҳлар ва кўрсаткичлар муаллифи ва нашрга тайёрловчилар: А.Аҳмад, Ҳ.Бобобеков; Масъул муҳаррир Б.Эшпўлатов. Нашрлар ва матбаачилар гуруҳи: И.Шоғуломов ва бошқалар. – Т.: Шарқ, 1997. – Б.290-291.
4. Kenjaev, S. N. o'g'li. (2022). Amir Temurning Xitoy bilan munosabatlari va Tayzi o'g'lon faoliyati. *Science and Education*, 3(5), 1493-1497. Retrieved from <https://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/3603>

5. Sardor Nurmurodovich Kenjayev, Komron Mahmud o'g'li Zayniev. Amir Temur davlati va Xitoy Min sulolasi aloqalarida otlar savdosi xususida. Vol. 3 No. (2022): Science and Education. 634-639.
6. Кенжаев С.Амир Темур ва Хитой давлати ўртасидаги ҳарбий муносабатлар ўзаро тўқнашув хавфининг вужудга келиши // ЎЗМУ ХАБАРЛАРИ, 2022. № 1/9. – Б.18.
7. Сардор Кенжаев. АМИР ТЕМУР ДАВЛАТИ ВА ХИТОЙ (МИН) ИМПЕРИЯСИ ЎРТАСИДАГИ САВДО АЛОҚАЛАРИ ТАРИХИДАН // ЎТМИШГА НАЗАР, 4 ЖИЛД, 10 СОН. – Б.67.
8. Kenjayev S.N. Amir Temur's Ambassadorial Activity in Diplomatic Relations with China (Min State)(In the Case of Fu An) //- Miasto Przyszłości, 2022. 112-114 p.
9. Сардор Кенжаев. АМИР ТЕМУР ВА ХИТОЙ ДИПЛОМАТИК МУНОСАБАТЛАРИНИНГ ОБЪЕКТИВ ВА СУБЪЕКТИВ ОМИЛЛАРИ// Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 2022. 130-135 б.
10. Kenjayev S.N. Trade and Economic Relations between Amir Temur's State and the Min Dynasty//- " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM, 2021. 480-481
11. Сардор КЕНЖАЕВ. EMERGENCE OF THE RISK OF CONFLICT IN MILITARY RELATIONS BETWEEN AMIR TIMUR AND THE CHINESE STATE//.-Тошкент, 2022.